

WILL THEY STAY? JOB SATISFACTION AND DISSATISFACTION AMONG NOVICE TEACHERS

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Abstract:

There is a symbiotic relationship between students' motivation to learn and the way teachers teach. Students are motivated and inspired by great teachers. There are many inspiring success stories of students who named their teachers as their role model and icon for success. As such, teaching can be a rewarding or a challenging task to teachers. However, lack of motivation from teachers can have a negative impact on students' learning. Some teachers may begin their career being highly motivated but ended up losing the motivation as years go by. There are many determinants that act as satisfaction and dissatisfaction job factors among novice teachers. This study looks into the factors affecting novice teachers' motivation in the workforce. 176 novice teachers responded to a survey on what caused them to be satisfied and dissatisfied with teaching. Findings reveal that novice lecturers are satisfied by some factors to make them effective at work; yet can be dissatisfied by certain issues surrounding the institution.

Keywords: institution, novice lecturers, satisfaction factors, dissatisfaction factors

1. Introduction

According to Huitt (2011), there are many factors that can motivate students to learn. Generally, students are motivated to learn from extrinsic and intrinsic factors (Figure 1). Intrinsic factors refer to the cognitive, affective and conative abilities of the learners. On the other hand, some examples of extrinsic factors are (a) operant conditioning and (b) social cognition. In operant condition, learning is influenced by consequences-reinforcement and punishment. In social cognition, learning takes place in social

settings. Here, the teacher plays an important role in providing positive extrinsic motivation to learners. Teachers can also provide conducive learning to enhance positive intrinsic motivation in learners. Intrinsic motivation promotes life-long learning.

Figure 1: Motivation to Learn (adapted for Huitt, 2011)

According to Livingstone (2009), there is an influence of teachers' motivation on students' academic achievement. The study reveals that students' academic performance is dependent on teachers' monetary rewards. Students' academic performance is also dependent on teachers' non-monetary rewards. There is also a significant relationship between monetary and non-monetary rewards on students' academic performance. The study also reveals that motivation is instrumental in maintaining students' outstanding academic performance.

Novice lecturers enter the teaching profession with or without any teaching experience. At the beginning of their teaching career, they would be required to attend courses to improve their teaching skills. One of the main determinants to successful classroom learning is effective teaching. With reference to Figure 2, according to Santrock (2009), effective teaching is the combination of teachers' professional knowledge and skills, as well as their commitment and motivation. According to Gultekin and Acap (2014), the role of motivation is very crucial in the teaching and learning experience in the classroom. The teachers' motivation (or lack of it) has proven to impact students' learning motivation. As far as academic qualifications and work requirements are concerned, new lecturers are appointed based on their academic and professional skills.

The teaching skills of lecturers can be improved through in-house and external training. However, commitment and motivation are the more complex components as these components cannot be taught or achieved through training. Educational institutions provide on-going training for novice teachers. Some become more

motivated to improve their teaching, while some need more “push” in their career. Over the years, novice teachers would be encouraged to increase their knowledge as well as teaching skills. Teaching is a career that requires commitment. Teachers need to be motivated so that they can stay long in the teaching profession. Teaching is often said to be a form of art. This is because effective teaching does not only require the teacher to master the professional knowledge and skills to be applied in the classrooms. Teachers need to be committed to their teaching so that learners are happy to learn in the classroom environment. In addition to that, the job scope of a teacher may include other non-teaching responsibilities. Thus, teachers need motivation to persevere when responsibilities increase and teaching-learning conditions are not favourable.

Figure 2: Effective Teaching (Santrock, 2009)

The main objective of this study is to explore the contributing factors that influence work motivation among novice lecturers. Specifically, this study looks at what causes novice lecturers to be satisfied and dissatisfied with their work. This research is done to answer the following questions:

1. Is there any significant difference for satisfaction and dissatisfaction factors across academic qualification for novice lecturers?
2. Is there any significant difference for satisfaction and dissatisfaction factors across genders for novice lecturers?
3. In what ways do the satisfaction factors influence the perception of teaching for novice lecturers?
4. In what ways do the dissatisfaction factors influence the perception of teaching for novice lecturers?

2. Literature Review

2.1 Theoretical Framework of the Study

This study is rooted from the two-factor theory of work motivation by Sincero (2012). According to the theory, two main factors contribute to work motivation and they are (a) satisfaction, and (b) dissatisfaction factors (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Work Motivation (adapted from Sicero, 2012)

2.2 Satisfaction Factors

Satisfaction factors are motivation factors that act as pushing factors for the novice lecturers to enjoy working. Some of the factors are altruistic (intrinsic) and extrinsic. Novice lecturers can also be influenced by others.

2.3 Dissatisfaction Factors

Dissatisfaction factors are factors to be addressed by the workplace. Among some dissatisfaction factors are the nature of the teaching profession, the curriculum, the work conditions, students and their parents, colleagues and administrators as well as physical conditions.

2.4 Past Studies

Mangaleswarasharma (2017) explored the motivation and job satisfaction of teachers with the objectives to study the factors related to the choice of their job and their job satisfaction. The population of the study was teachers in Sri Lanka and the target population of the study consisted of teachers in three districts in Northern Sri Lanka. 150 teachers participated in a workshop was purposively selected for this study. A self-developed questionnaire, built up by reviewing related literature was used for data collection. Quantitative data collected through questionnaire survey was analyzed using simple descriptive statistics including frequencies and percentages. Findings from the study showed that 79% of the teachers agreed that they selected teaching profession on their own choice and made sure they were qualified for the profession. 82% of them were involved in teaching with full satisfaction. However, 29% of the teachers wanted

to do some other jobs. The results of this study also indicated that, teachers selected this profession as they preferred it; it is a permanent job and it has long holidays and less working hours. Among the teachers who taught with full satisfaction, 45% expressed that they loved it. Based on the findings, the study concluded that, teachers were motivated towards their profession.

The study by Sajid and Shaheen (2013) was designed to examine factors which were responsible for influencing high and low motivational level of university academicians. Two factors namely, class room environment, work load stress were taken as independent variables while motivation was taken as dependent variable. Quantitative data were collected through questionnaire containing dichotomous scales. The findings of the study revealed that classroom environment was responsible for high level of motivation, while work-load stress caused low motivation among academicians.

Next, the research by Bentea and Anghelache (2012) explored differences of job satisfaction across gender. It also looked into the professional positions given by the level of continuous training held, and the dominant needs of the teachers. The sample consisted of 122 Romanian teachers from primary, secondary and high schools. Findings did not show differences between men and women in overall job satisfaction and its dimensions. However, the results revealed that satisfaction was affected by the level of continuous training. Also, job satisfaction was influenced by the intensity of the needs of achievement and affiliation.

Finally, the study by Mark (2015) identified factors influencing teachers' motivation and job performance in public secondary schools in Kibaha District, specifically looking at factors of motivation that can lead to a teacher's job satisfaction and dissatisfaction in public secondary schools. The study also assessed factors of motivation that are available at good performing schools and that are not available at poor performing schools and to document suggestions for improving teacher's job satisfaction and performance. The findings of the study showed that motivation of teachers in Kibaha District was affected by factors such as poor working conditions, poor communication among colleagues, low salary/pay, unfavorable policies on education, delays in promotions and community's negative perception towards teaching.

3. Material and Methods

3.1 Research Design, Population and Sample

This study employs the descriptive design using survey method. The population chosen was newly appointed lecturers who have just started their teaching career for less than one year. 176 novice lecturers were randomly chosen to respond to the survey.

3.2 Data Collection Procedure and Data Analysis

The novice lecturers responded to a 3 part survey; Section A is about their demographic profile, section B looks at the satisfaction factors and section C looks at the

dissatisfaction factors. The responses were analysed using SPSS for mean scores and t-test scores.

4. Results and Discussion

This section discusses the findings based on the research questions.

- (a) Research Question 1: Is there any significant difference for satisfaction and dissatisfaction factors across academic qualification for novice lecturers?

Table 1: Group statistics academic qualification-satisfaction factors

	Academic Qualification	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Satisfaction factors	masters	161	2.0615	.34407	.02712
	PhD	15	2.2767	.36296	.09372

Table 2: Independent Samples Test for academic qualification-satisfaction factors

	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances	t-test for Equality of Means								
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Satisfaction factors	Equal variances assumed	.000	.998	-2.306	174	.022	-.21518	.09330	-.39933	-.03102
	Equal variances not assumed			-2.206	16.432	.042	-.21518	.09756	-.42155	-.00880

Table 3: Difference on lecturers in satisfaction factors by academic qualification

Variables	n	Mean	S.D.	t	p
Qualification				-2.31	.02
Masters	161	2.06	.34		
PhD	15	2.28	.36		

An independent sample t-test was performed to examine the difference between masters and PhD qualification in satisfaction factors as shown in Table 2 and 3. The results indicated that the mean score for masters ($M = 2.06$, $SD = .34$) and PhD ($M = 2.28$, $SD = .36$) was a statistically significant difference in the mean score ($t(174) = -2.31$), $p = .02$) at the 0.05 level. This finding is in accordance with the study by Mangaleswarasharma (2017) who also found that teachers are satisfied with their job when they had chosen the profession and had made sure they were qualified for the teaching post they chose.

Table 4: Group Statistics-dissatisfaction factors

	Academic Qualification	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Dissatisfaction factors	masters	161	2.4985	.56957	.04489
	PhD	15	2.7826	.29625	.07649

Table 5: Independent Samples Test for dissatisfaction factors

	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances	t-test for Equality of Means								
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Dissatisfaction actors	Equal variances assumed	6.578	0.011	-1.904	174	0.059	-0.28409	0.14918	-0.5785	0.01034
	Equal variances not assumed			-3.203	25.043	0.004	-0.28409	0.08869	-0.4667	-0.10145

Table 6: Difference for lecturers' dissatisfaction factors by academic qualification

Variables	n	Mean	S.D.	t	p
Qualification				-1.90	0.06
Masters	161	2.50	.57		
PhD	15	2.78	.30		

The results revealed the mean score of masters are ($M = 2.50$, $SD = .57$) and PhD ($M = 2.78$, $SD = .30$). An independent sample t-test was performed to examine the difference between masters and PhD in dissatisfaction factors as shown in Table 5 and 6. T-test indicated that there was no statistically significant difference in the mean score ($t(174) = -1.90$, $p = .06$) at the 0.05 level. This means that academic qualification among novice lecturers was not an indicator of job dissatisfaction.

(b) Research Question 2: Is there any significant difference for satisfaction and dissatisfaction factors across genders for novice lecturers?

Table 7: Group statistics-satisfaction factors for satisfaction factors across gender

	Academic Qualification	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Satisfaction factors	masters	54	2.1157	.35592	.04844
	PhD	122	2.0639	.34744	.03146

Table 8: Independent Samples Test satisfaction factors across gender

	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances	t-test for Equality of Means								
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Satisfaction factors	Equal variances assumed	.056	.814	.905	174	.366	.05181	.05721	-.06112	.16473
	Equal variances not assumed			.897	99.391	.372	.05181	.05775	-.06278	.16640

Table 9: Difference on lecturers in motivating factors by academic qualification

Variables	n	Mean	S.D.	t	p
Qualification				.91	.35
Masters	54	2.12	.36		
PhD	122	2.06	.35		

An independent sample t-test was performed to examine the difference between male and female lecturers in satisfaction factors as shown in Table 8 and 9. The results indicated that the mean score of male ($M = 2.12$, $SD = .36$) and female ($M = 2.06$, $SD = .35$) was no statistically significant difference in the mean score ($t(174) = .91$), $p = .37$) at the 0.05 level. This finding is in accordance with the research by Bentea and Anghelache (2012) who also reported there were no differences in satisfaction factors across gender.

Table 10: group statistics-dissatisfaction factors across gender

	Academic Qualification	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Dissatisfaction factors	masters	54	2.6546	.46364	.06309
	PhD	122	2.4644	.58560	.05302

Table 11: Independent Samples Test for dissatisfaction factors across gender

	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances	t-test for Equality of Means								
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Dissatisfaction factors	Equal variances assumed	2.806	.096	2.111	174	.036	.19023	.09011	.01237	.36808
	Equal variances not assumed			2.308	126.621	.023	.19023	.08241	.02715	.35331

Table 12: Difference of lecturers in dissatisfaction factors by academic qualification

Variables	n	Mean	S.D.	t	p
Qualification				2.11	.04
Masters	54	2.65	.46		
PhD	122	2.46	.59		

An independent sample t-test was performed to examine the difference between male and female lecturers in demotivating factors as shown in Table 11 and 12. The results indicated that the mean score of male ($M = 2.65$, $SD = .46$) and female ($M = 2.46$, $SD = .59$) and this finding indicated statistically significant difference in the mean score ($t(174) = 2.11$, $p = .04$) at the 0.05 level. This interesting finding, although is not accordance with the study by Bentea and Anghelache (2012), showed how different gender perceive the dissatisfaction factors in the teaching profession differently.

(c) Research Question 3: In what ways do the satisfaction factors influence the perception of teaching for novice lecturers?

Figure 3: Bar chart of mean scores for Satisfaction Factors

Figure 3 above shows the bar chart for mean scores for satisfaction factors. Among some of the highest mean were; highest regard for education (3.2), media influence (2.9), higher salary (2.8) and also more holidays (2.8). The study by Bentea and Anghelache (2012) also reported that teachers regard highly the opportunities of continuous education in their profession. In addition to that, Mangaleswarasharma (2017) also reported similar findings for teachers who actually chose the profession for its “more holidays” perks.

(d) Research Question 4: In what ways do the dissatisfaction factors influence their perception of teaching for novice lecturers?

Figure 4: Bar Chart showing mean scores for Dissatisfaction factors

Figure 4 above shows the mean scores for dissatisfaction factors. The highest mean are; they felt they could not communicate with colleagues (4.1) and administrators (3.9). This finding is in accordance with the findings by Mark (2015) who also found that communication among fellow colleagues can affect their work motivation.

5. Conclusion

5.1 Summary of Findings

Overall, this current research showed interesting findings. There were significant differences for satisfaction factors for academic qualification among lecturers as well as dissatisfaction factors across genders. There were no significant differences for dissatisfaction factors for academic qualification and satisfaction factors across gender. In addition, mean scores revealed that some satisfaction factors among novice lecturers are the opportunities for continuing education, media influence in making the job attractive, the high salary offered and also the fact that they would have more holidays

compared to other professions. On the other hand, some factors like lack of communication among colleagues and administrators may cause dissatisfaction. The factors that contribute to satisfaction could be further improved so novice lecturers would remain in the teaching profession longer. In addition to that, the factors that cause dissatisfaction need to be addressed by the affecting (not sure affecting or affected) parties so that novice lectures who stay continue to be motivated to teach.

5.2 Suggestion for Future Research

Future research could look into the relationship between years of service and teaching satisfaction/dissatisfaction among lecturers. The high mobility across institutions among lecturers may not be merely because of salary perks, and if dissatisfaction factors are addressed earlier, institutions need not lose lecturers to other (teaching positions or jobs).

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